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Fire properties of natural fibre composites

DEVELOPMENT OF FIRE RETARDANT PLYS FOR USE IN
NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE

Overview

- Why fire properties
- Methodology
- Ply development
 - Characterisation
 - Results
 - Outcomes and findings
- Fire retardant ply
 - Characterisation
 - Results
 - Outcomes and findings

Why fire properties?

Why fire properties?

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Why fire properties?

- ECE Regulation 118 Annex 6 – horizontal and vertical
- FAR 25.853 – Horizontal and vertical
- ISO5660 – 1:2015
- ASTM E1321 – 13
- ... and more

Methodology

- Manufacture plies
- TGA of plies
- Composite manufacture
- TGA of composites
- Fire testing - cone calorimetry
- 4-point bending

Methodology

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) - monitoring the mass of a substance as a function of temperature or time, when subjected to a controlled temperature.

Methodology

Cone calorimetry - a bench scale test that provides a variety of fire properties during the combustion of a sample.

Ply development

- Raw material availability (fibres)
- Easy of processing
- Manufacturing method
- Can be used in liquid composite moulding (LCM)
- Material properties
- Waste product use - nice to have

Ply development

Sugarcane bagasse

Ply development

Ply development

Ply development

Ply development

Characterisation

Characterisation

Outcomes and findings

- Feasible to make sugar-cane bagasse ply which can be used in LCM process
- Comparable fire properties to non-woven hemp fabric, but not mechanical properties

Fire retardant ply

- Similar ply manufacturing process used
- Four retardants
 - AP422 - Ammonium polyphosphate
 - ATH - Aluminium trihydroxide
 - Calcium carbonate - eggshells
 - Lignin
- Compare to bulk filled composite with plain plies

Ply development

Characterisation

Characterisation

Outcomes and findings

- Feasible to make plies with retardants embedded - shown with TGA
- APP plies performed best
- APP bulk filled composite had the increased fire performance of all samples
- Flexural modulus lowest for APP plies, but highest for APP filled composite - more testing would be required to establish correlation

Questions

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Thank you

Asanka Basnayake | PhD Student
School of Mechanical and Mining Engineering
p.basnayake@uq.edu.au

Image references

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